

A Study on Issues in Marketing of Life Insurance Services in India

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Abstract

Insurance and economic development in India manifest straight effective correlation on the ballooning track way. Insurance companies, both life and nonlife, have been playing the role of financial conciliator and accomplish remarkably useful functions in our economy. In India, Insurance sector was opened for private participation with the enactment of the IDRA Act 1999. Since then, 22 private companies have been established in life insurance sector. All these players are actively introducing inventive products to meet the peculiar needs of intended policyholders. However, life insurance companies, particularly private sector players, give additional consciousness in selling unit liked plans that are not suited to the real needs of the insured. This paper shows the important aspects of life insurance marketing activity from a services point of view and highlights the present issues and challenges facing the life insurance companies in product marketing. Overall my paper shows the important aspects of life insurance sectors challenges, opportunities facing the life insurance companies in product marketing.

Keywords: Life Insurance, Insurance Service marketing, Issues and challenges etc.

Introduction

Marketing, as the term is commonly understood today was developed initially in connection with the selling of consumer packaged goods and later with the selling of industrial goods. The committee on definitions of the American marketing Association defined marketing as the performance of business activities that direct the flow of goods and services to the consumer. Insurance marketing is basically just the marketing of insurance products. Insurance marketing focuses the importance of the customer linking and priorities. Major objectives of life insurance marketing are increasing customer awareness, successful distribution of insurance products, developing corporate image, improving customer service, improving customer base and its spread and etc.

Life insurance is a contract between the insurer and policy owner. Insurer is agreed to pay an amount to the person insured or his nominee either at the date of maturity or a periodic interval or unfortunate death of the policy owner. Policy owner has to pay a

fixed amount called premium in periodic intervals. This can be monthly, quarterly, half yearly, or yearly. Policy owner is allowed to choose the type of payment and payment cycle. Premium amount varies depending on many factors like age of the policy owner, scheme, type of the policy, sum-assured etc. Premium amount once fixed cannot be changed later.

It is a contract in which the insurance company, in consideration of a premium paid either in lump sum or installments, undertake to the person for whose benefit the policy is undertaken, a certain sum of money on the death of the insured or on the expiry of the policy, whichever occurs first. For the sum assured in the event of death. At present, life insurance enjoys maximum scope because life insurance enjoys maximum scope because life is the most important asset to the society or an individual. Each and every person requires this insurance. Insurance companies, both life and non-life, have been playing the role of financial intermediaries and performing extremely useful functions in our economy. In India insurance sector was opened for private participation with the enactment of the IRDA Act, 1999. Since then, 22 private sector have been established in life insurance sector. All these players were introduced innovative products to meet the specific needs of the prospective policyholders.

Service Marketing

- Product
- Price
- Promotion
- Place
- People
- Process
- Physical Evidence

Product

Services are products even though intangible they are things. And service marketers must always remember that consumers do not buy any products, they buy attributes that are converted into benefits. Like other consumer “good” services are either convenience, shopping or specialty goods with all that implies many services are custom designed products. Services are intangible and heterogeneous and cannot easily be separated from their producers.

Price

The price policies for service marketers tend to parallel those used throughout the general field of marketing. The pricing goals of service marketers vary, but typically the pricing goal of most is to maximize profits for each sale not necessarily the wisest pricing practice. Other pricing goals of service marketers are to (i) attract new business and (ii) increase sales volume.

Promotion

Promotion is an important part of marketing. To successfully promote services, they must be made to have a favorable positive image constructed to project attributes of the services.

Place

Channels of distribution for intangible dominant products such as services are generally limited to the buyers and sellers. Group Insurance plans written through employers, labour unions, and professional associations have also become extremely successful.

People

The people lives in inseparability of the product/ consumption interface, and therefore the satisfaction of not only the recipient of the service, that is the customer, but also the providers of the service, that is the company's own personnel become extremely important.

Process

First the inseparability characteristic of services has an important implication for how the service company's personnel deliver the service to the customer and how the customer participates in the service delivery process.

Physical Evidence

Since a service is inherently intangible, it is important for the client to search for tangible or physical clauses which enable them to evaluate the service.

Conclusion

The Insurance company was previously a monopoly institution in the Life Insurance business. But now the corporation is in the position to face competition from private insurance companies. Since, the corporation is going to face competition from the private life insurance companies it has to improve its efficiency at all levels.

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